

NEWSLETTER

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 Decido

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“ Governments and public administrations are increasingly aware of the importance of involving citizens in the design, creation and implementation of public services. ”

DECIDO MAPPING OF STAKEHOLDERS

This involvement of citizens in public affairs has several beneficial effects, such as the achievement of more efficient, effective and democratic public services, as well as higher levels of trust in governments and the political class.

We call this involvement co-creation or co-production of public services and, in the case of DECIDO, this paradigm is used for the design of policies in several areas related to disaster risk management such as floods, fires, power outages or assistance to war refugees.

To design the co-creation methodology in DECIDO, we have reviewed 119 documents related to concepts such as co-creation, co-design, co-production and design of public services, in particular emergency services.

In addition, in order to build on developments in co-creation carried out by other projects that have addressed this topic, we have paid special attention to the following projects funded by the European Commission:

- **COCKPIT:** Citizens Collaboration and Co-Creation in Public Service Delivery (2010-2012).
- **LIVING LAB:** Design Study for the LIVING LAB Research Infrastructure, to research human interaction with, and stimulate the adoption of, sustainable, smart and healthy innovations around the home (2008-2010).
- **ENLARGE:** ENergies for Local Administrations: Renovate Governance in Europe (2016-2018).
- **CITADEL:** Empowering Citizens to Transform European Public Administrations (2016-2019).
- **COSIE:** Co-creation of service innovation in Europe (2017-2021).
- **Co-VAL:** Understanding value co-creation in public services for transforming European public administrations (2018-2021).

DECIDO's co-creation methodology is made up of the 4 steps that we consider to constitute the Policy Life Cycle:

- **Agenda setting:** this step involves understanding in detail the challenges to be addressed and planning all the resources needed to carry out the co-creation process.
- **Policy formulation:** this step involves setting out the challenges and looking for effective and acceptable courses of action to address them. This is the phase we call hackathon, in the sense that it is a meeting of stakeholders with the common goal of finding solutions to a challenge in a collaborative way.
- **Implementation and maintenance:** in this step, the prototype responses to the challenges that have been designed in the previous stage are implemented and made available to stakeholders.
- **Evaluation:** Evaluation involves analysing the performance data of the systems after their implementation (procedures/policies) and assessing whether it is necessary to repeat the co-creation process either from the beginning or from one of its phases.

The co-creation methodology with the detail of the 4 steps mentioned above and the interactions between their sub-steps is shown in the following figure:

Story

Update Post Post to gather more data

To Do

Validate we are only capturing data we want

Auto opt-out Amazon Data

New email opt for non-opted

In Progress

update tool to capture more form fields

Post Tech Debt

Done

Poc Post updates

Update Standard Post Block for New Post

Assign email to user
Data written to DB
Deploy as no prod

Pull Data on Copy + Title

Goals

- Create Proof # Corresponding
- MVP - Connect existing What w today.

Backlog

- New service to collect + store data from updates story
- Create new endpoint for data to flow to
- Improv Pipeline Exp To
- Fix base usage
- Company Data Store
Create Company API endpoint

MVP Data Store

CI/CD

Monitoring + Alerts

Time User -> API

Photo by Jacek Dylag on Unsplash

ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE FINNISH PILOT ON FOREST FIRES

The period from September 2022 until March 2023 has been used to finalize the agenda setting process of the Finnish pilot. Stakeholders convened to understand problems around forest fires and agree on the steps moving forward towards improving policies for forest fires. The stakeholder group consisted of both national and Kainuu Region organizations.

The benefit of a wide range of organizations participating provides 1) a broad expertise relevant to forest fires, 2) greater resources for policy development, 3) insight into departmental and interdepartmental challenges and needs to facilitate policy development and implementation, 4) as well as data needed to inform decision making throughout the policy development process.

Kainuu organizations participating were the Kainuu Rescue Department (host), City of Kajaani, and the Kainuu Social Welfare Authority (social and healthcare services), while national organizations included the Finnish Forestry Centre, Emergency Services College, and the Finnish National Rescue Association. Using the DECIDO portal, the group collaboratively worked in the problem identification and ideation processes. The theme of forest fires was used to guide working groups, and key objectives to address aspects of forest fires were developed. Each participant provided their point of view, and two guiding principles were used to guide the working: 1) Organizational needs, and 2) civilian needs (Figure 1). From these two principles, three objectives were crea-

ted to address organizational and civilian needs both during prevention and preparedness, and during incidents.

The formulated policy uses the working title **“Risk mitigation and preparedness for forest fires”**. During the policy formulation process, a significant number of problems were identified. For each of the problems, stakeholders offered a series of approaches and ideas. The stakeholder groups narrowed down the list of ideas and agreed to trial proposals based on individual and group criteria. The proposals were categorized into **three objectives within the policy**: 1) **Resourcing** – Identification and sharing of available resource information among direct emergency actors and support organizations, 2) **Citizen Safety During Emergencies** - Means to evacuate, shelter, and keep track of citizens for a limited amount of time during emergencies, and 3) **Prevention and preparedness planning** - Mitigation strategies to reduce forest fire risk and educate citizens (formal and informal ways) on emergency actions.

In the following weeks, the final phases of the policy development cycle will be conducted. The stakeholders will simulate the policy and evaluate the outcomes. As part of the policy development process, citizens will be involved as well. The DECIDO portal will be used to present the policy draft to collect feedback and address the opinions and concerns of citizens with the policy. Citizens have been engaged through physi-

cal public events throughout Kainuu, and will be consulted in future events as well. The policy developed through DECIDO is part of the regional strategy where evacuation center introductions are being held, and citizens participate in significant numbers. Therefore, feedback from the organized evacuation center events can be directly built into the policy development work as part of DECIDO.

Following the completion of the first policy development cycle, a second round of meetings is planned for the autumn period of 2023. In the autumn period, the outcomes of the policy will be evaluated, and more recent data used to further improve the policy, which will contribute to the work and operation of the newly formed Kainuu Welfare County.

Figure 1 Organizational needs and civilian needs

GREEK PILOT ACHIEVEMENTS ON MANAGING POWER OUTAGES IN HALKI

From September 2022 until March 2023, the Greek Pilot team has established a stakeholders group consisting of individuals from different sectors to provide valuable input and guidance on the project’s development. This group has proved to be a crucial factor for given useful feedback on the project.

In addition, the Greek Pilot team has made significant progress towards achieving the project’s goals. They have conducted three successful hackathons that brought together diverse stakeholders to generate innovative solutions to address the power outages in Halki. These hackathons were highly successful, resulting in a wealth of ideas and insights.

Furthermore, two co-creation sessions were held which facilitated collaboration between stakeholders and the project team. These sessions were designed to identify and address any issues that arose during the project’s development, ensuring a comprehensive and inclusive approach to policy development.

The project team has also demonstrated the DECIDO portal to stakeholders and conducted training sessions to equip them with the necessary tools and knowledge to use the portal effectively. The portal has proved to be an essential tool for data sharing.

In order to ensure a data-driven approach to the development of the Policy, the Greek Pilot team launched a survey to collect additional data on

emergencies and power outages in Halki. This survey offered valuable insight into the community’s needs and enabled a more comprehensive approach, highlighting citizens’ involvement in the process.

Finally, the Greek Pilot team is combing data from existing datasets, hackathons, and survey responses to create the first Policy draft on power outages in the Municipality of Halki. This will be accomplished through another co-creation session, where stakeholders will provide feedback and suggestions for the policy’s initiation and improvement. The DECIDO portal was thoroughly reviewed and utilised during the policy creation phase, providing both the stakeholders and the pilot team with a user-friendly environment to collaborate and share information.

As a result, in the next few weeks, a Policy is going to be created focusing on improving the preparation and management of a power outage event, highlighting the possibility of an upcoming blackout and on energy demand forecasting - energy conservation and recommending insightful actions for the local authority to prevent the crisis of a power outage event. The next steps will be to further refine this Policy so that depending on the season and weather conditions, respective alerts and adaptation actions will be sent to social actors and subsequently to citizens.

These achievements demonstrate the commitment of the Greek Pilot team to the success of the DECIDO project and highlight their significant contribution to the project’s development.

Figure 1: Policy Implementation and Policy Evaluation phase

DECIDO IN TORINO: MOVING FORWARD

Within the framework of the DECIDO project, the last months of 2022 in Torino were dedicated to a number of restricted meetings and larger hackathons dealing with the policy formulation step of the policy life cycle process for all the three pilots locally identified.

The challenge to be addressed were the following.

1. To improve the communication pattern toward citizens in view of potential flood emergencies. There are several experiment aiming at improving the communication between first responders and citizens. In early 2023 the team worked to design specific alert messages tailored to the specific needs of groups of citizens with different socio cultural profiles: residents, drivers, elderly people, students, street vendors, business owners.

2. To better clarify to fragile people, taken care by the food bank distribution system, the healthy condition of the food distributed for free beyond its expiry date, but way before its recommended consumption interval. In early 2023 the team designed simplified labels to be applied on the products and clearly stating the latter interval, rather than the expiry date.

3. To simplify the process, for Ukrainian refugees, of getting proper and precise information on Italian regulations. Given the lack of native speakers Ukrainian native cultural mediators,

local institutions struggle to channel the proper information and the refugees struggle to understand it, in very sensitive domains like housing and health care, residence permits, schooling, job orientation and leisure time. In early 2023 the team developed a first HTML draft of a web portal gathering such info from official channels and making them available in Ukrainian. The following step, still ongoing, is the simulation of the policy implementation phase of the policy life cycle process. The three pilots are at different levels of maturity and readiness. The actual process of re-labelling the food distributed for free by food banks has started already, and after two rounds in February 2023 and different types of product labelled, some very first feedbacks are being collected both from fragile citizens and food banks.

An HTML draft of a web portal is in place and again in February 2023, Ukrainian volunteers started translating a first batch of useful contents soon to be uploaded and tested, after a proper training on how to use the portal will have taken place. Last but not least, the traditional, generic and often unclear weather alert messages were tweaked, with the help of trained psychologists, into more understandable and targeted ones. The next challenge will be to identify a control group of citizens and run an actual simulation and understand the proper technological infrastructure for doing so.

Stay tuned with the project DECIDO in order to know what will happen next in Torino.

FROM AGENDA SETTING

Flood emergency in two areas of the city of Turin, along the River Po: Murazzi and Meisino Park

Fighting against the food waste, in the context of increased basic needs following the Covid-19 pandemic

Helping asylum seekers from Ukraine, to be welcomed in the best possible way after their arrival in Turin

Targeted alert messages depending on the type of weather phenomenon and on the categories of recipients

New food labelling for food banks, with reference to ministerial tables with recommended consumption intervals for the different types of products

Web portal updated by volunteers, identifying the concrete needs and requests from Ukrainian refugees

TO POLICY FORMULATION

PILOT ARAGON REGION

In the pilot of the Aragon region, three relevant events have been carried out, consisting of a technical hackathon of space apps, a datathon in which datasets were identified and a process of co-creation of policies on “data alliance”. These are presented in more detail below.

First event: Space apps

More than 60 people gathered at Etopia, center of art and technology (Zaragoza) to participate in the ninth edition of the hackathon organized by NASA SpaceAppsChallenge on 1st October 2022. This hackathon is considered the largest on the planet. Not in vain, in its previous edition more than 28,000 people from 162 countries registered, developing more than 2814 projects.

The idea behind this event is to use the data sources offered by NASA - along with any other source of information that the participant considers necessary - to solve a series of problems and challenges that the American space agency itself proposes prior to the contest. This event was sponsored by Ibercivis and H2020-DECIDO, supported the organization of the local event in Zaragoza by mentoring solutions for the challenge Earth Data analysis, developers wanted. 14 work teams that provided 14 solutions to the challenges posed, aligned with DECIDO’s objectives.

The No rocket no paradise team developed a

cell-based fire spread simulator that uses NASA’s open data for geographic data and ground conditions. They opted to model fire using the Rothermel simple fire model, a well-established fire spread model capable of quantifying how fast it moves through terrain. The simulation is able to predict safe and dangerous areas, along with the time it will take to burn.

Second event: Datathon identifying datasets
Last November 25th took place the datathon “The Future of Data” organized by Aragon Open Data, on the occasion of the tenth anniversary of this open data portal of the Government of Aragon. Each participating team was challenged to work on the creation of new useful services for society, based on the open data available on the Aragón Open Data platform.

The proposed challenges were: connecting with nature, more lively neighborhoods, employment opportunities, university life, getting to know Aragon, renewable energies, knowing and preventing the problem of forest fires.

Ibercivis, as part of the consortium of the DECIDO project and promoter of its pilot project in Aragon together with SARGA/Government of Aragon, proposed the identification of datasets and design of a digital service to facilitate the prevention of forest fires in the Community of Aragon

Some of the datasets from the Aragon Open

Data Portal:

- Data from the Register of Installation and/or Maintenance Companies (fire protection systems)
- Forest fires and forest area affected, by municipalities, counties and provinces. in Aragón.
- Agricultural varieties and crops
- Agricultural regions in aragon
- Vegetation and land use
- Critical areas designated for the protection of endangered species in Aragon
- Natural Resources Management Plans in Aragon

Third event: The data alliance

On Friday, February 17, a test of the process of creation and evaluation of public policies based on data was carried out with the participation of young Aragonese students from middle and high school.

The public policy decision-making cycle is composed of four phases. First, an analysis of the data is carried out and, based on this data, solutions or public policy proposals are designed. In the third stage, these are implemented and indicators or meters are chosen to determine their effectiveness measured in the fourth phase, entering once again into a process of analysis and design.

In this case, it was decided to simulate the first and second phases, an analysis of the data and a decision making process for public policies, considering the problem of the fires in Aragon, especially those of the last year as the objective of the DECIDO pilot.

In the first phase, a data-driven analysis of the problem was performed. The importance of the problem was explained and they were urged to look for possible solutions to alleviate the problem.

The second phase dealt with how to develop public policies and proposed solutions divided into institutional actions, localized actions and localized actions. Some of the proposals were: risk light to avoid work with fire risk, improve temperature monitoring system for quick action in case of fire, raise awareness and learning to farmers about the machinery and improve the machinery used in the field.

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CONSORTIUM

